

Automated Shift For Time-Temperature Superposition

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SUMMARY: Time-temperature superposition has been used for long-term structural durability design with short-term accelerating tests at elevated temperatures. Knowledge of a master curve at a specific reference temperature along with time-temperature shift factors serves to completely characterize the material or the failure properties across an enormous spectrum of times through the temperatures. A user-friendly tool to automatically obtain the master curve, the shift factors and the reliability is developed, and applied to several non-destructive and destructive properties successfully. With the tool, the time-temperature shifting becomes fast, objective and user-independent. The automated shifting tool is useful for not only the design of the structures, but acceleration of the accelerating tests.

KEYWORDS: durability design, time-temperature superposition, time-temperature shift factor, automated shift, generalized linear least-square fit, spreadsheet-based program.

INTRODUCTION

Accelerated testing has been an objective for research and engineering practice for many years. The conventional wisdom for acceleration then was to seek a database for large populations and/or to impose more severe test conditions. It was concluded that the key to acceleration was to understand the failure mechanism.

Polymeric materials and composites, whose matrix is polymeric material, are well known to exhibit time- and temperature-dependent failure. At load levels below short-time static strength, failure can occur sustained in duration in the time spectrum. The situation is somewhat similar to that of fatigue in metals. However, in polymers, even when the loads and stresses are completely constant in time, failure can still occur. This is known as creep failure. Furthermore, operation at elevated temperatures tends to shorten the life of these materials and their structures. These time- and temperature-dependency is a characteristic of viscoelastic materials.

These time- and temperature-dependent behaviors of the polymeric materials and composites lead to an accelerated testing method. Researchers have made an assumption based on an experimental evidence to show that the life of the viscoelastic materials can be accelerated by elevating temperature. This experimental evidence is called as *time-temperature equivalence* or *time-temperature superposition* [1]. Correspondence between the time and the temperature can be achieved by time-temperature shifting with suitable shift factors.

The master curve at a specific reference temperature plus the knowledge of the shift function versus temperature serve to completely characterize the material properties across an enormous spectrum of times through temperature. The method does not work well on semi-crystalline polymers, but it does work well on an amazing variety of polymers, including the epoxies and polyesters of interest to composites.

Another major advance has been made on the characterization of polymers and polymeric composites. This advancement of understanding is that the time-temperature shift hypothesis has been extended to cover failure properties by Miyano et al. [2]. In simplest terms, materials at constant strain rate taken to failure exhibit the behavior that the stress at failure versus the time to failure at various temperatures can be brought to a single unifying form by time-temperature shifting. This extension of the shift hypothesis to failure conditions is of extreme importance. Miyano [3] has extended the procedure or principle to include creep and fatigue conditions, and to a very wide variety of other conditions.

This time-temperature shifting method is powerful to the structural design because the long-term life can be estimated with the short-term test data. Many previous works have shown that the time-temperature shifting is applicable to the life estimation of the polymeric materials [1], composites [2, 3] and even jointed structures bonded with various types of adhesive materials [4].

However, the shifting itself has been very subjective and iterative. A shifter plots the data points at several temperatures, and uses their eyes to find the best shifting. When there is an addition of the new data, the shifter has to repeat this process. Since the data points are usually plotted in logarithmic time scale, a small amount of inaccurate shifting misleads to a large amount of error in life estimation. Furthermore, reliability calculation of the shifted data is essential to provide the design allowables. Therefore, it is essential to have a tool to do such things automatically.

TIME-TEMPERATURE SUPERPOSITION HYPOTHESIS

Creep functions and relaxation functions when displayed at various base temperatures on log-log scales show the following behavior. When the property functions at various temperatures are shifted along the logarithmic time axis, they can be brought into a superimposed form. As in Figure 1, curves at various elevated temperatures ($\dots, T_{i-1}, T_i, T_{i+1}, \dots$) can be shifted with respect to an arbitrarily selected reference temperature (T_o) to form an extended curve to long-term range. The extended curve is called a *master curve*.

Figure 1: Curves of creep compliance (D_c) on original ($\log t$) and shifted ($\log t'$) time scales.

It is well known that the ratio between the original time (t) and the shifted time (t') is mainly a function of temperature for many polymeric materials, and is called a time-temperature shift factor ($a_{T_o}(T) = t/t'$). Figure 2 shows a typical plot of the time-temperature shift factors as a function of temperature.

The shift factors can be correlated with the temperature by Arrhenius equation [1] as follows:

$$\log a_{T_o}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_o} \right) \quad (1)$$

where ΔH is the activation energy in [KJ/mol], and R is the gas constant, 8.314 [J/(°K·mol)]. The shift factors can thus be fit linearly on an inverse of temperature ($1/T$) scale. The physical meaning of the activation energy is a measure of energy barrier that must be overcome when molecular motion of the viscoelastic material is to occur. Thus, the activation energy changes drastically near the glass transition temperature (T_g), so that the curve of $\log a_{T_o}(T)$ versus $1/T$ usually has an inflection in the slope near the T_g . Figure 3 shows a typical plot of the time-temperature shift factors as a function of inverse of temperature. This bi-linear curve is used to easily extract any shift factors at any intermediate temperatures through the activation energy.

Figure 2: Time-temperature shift factors as a function of temperature.

Figure 3: Time-temperature shift factors as a function of inverse of temperature.

AUTOMATED SHIFT

A computer program, AutoShift, is developed as a tool for the automated shifting. The AutoShift is a spreadsheet-based program, running on Microsoft Excel®. Data inputs and a button press will achieve the followings automatically:

- 1) Shifter-independent time-temperature shifting.
- 2) Calculation of the time-temperature shift factors at each temperature.
- 3) Calculation the reliability of the shifted data.

The automated shifting begins with curve fitting of the test data at several temperatures. Once the curves are fitted, the data at elevated temperatures are mapped on to a reference curve by horizontal

movement. Shifting the curves with respect to a reference temperature (T_o) is achieved by calculating horizontal distances between the curves, as in Figure 1.

The AutoShift program uses a *General Linear Least-Square Method* to fit the data points at each temperature. A set of data points (x_i, y_i) is fit to a linear combination of any M specified functions of x . For example, the functions could be polynomials, $1, x, x^2, \dots, x^{M-1}$, in which case their general linear combination,

$$y(x) = a_1 + a_2x + a_3x^2 + \dots + a_Mx^{M-1} \quad (2)$$

is a polynomial of degree $(M-1)$. The general form of this kind of model is

$$y(x) = \sum_{k=1}^M a_k X_k(x) \quad (3)$$

where $X_1(x), \dots, X_M(x)$ are arbitrary fixed functions of x , called the *basis functions*. The basis functions can be any other functions, such as exponential or logarithmic functions.

Then a merit function (\mathbf{c}^2), which is defined as a sum of the distance between the data point and the fitted curve, is minimized to obtain a best curve fit. For this model, the merit function is written as

$$\mathbf{c}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{y_i - \sum_{k=1}^M a_k X_k(x_i)}{\mathbf{s}_i} \right]^2 \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{s}_i is the measurement error (standard deviation) of the i^{th} data point, presumed to be known. If the measurement errors are not known, they may all be set to a constant value $\mathbf{s} = 1$.

The minimum of Eq. (4) occurs when the derivative of \mathbf{c}^2 with respect to all M parameters a_k vanishes. This condition yields M equations

$$0 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\mathbf{s}_i^2} \left[y_i - \sum_{j=1}^M a_j X_j(x_i) \right] X_k(x_i), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (5)$$

Goodness of the curve fits is determined by

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SSE}{SST} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} SSE &= \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \\ SST &= \left(\sum y_i^2 \right) - \frac{(\sum y_i)^2}{N} \\ \hat{y}_i &= \sum_{k=1}^M a_k X_k(x_i) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The reliability of the fit curve (R^2) approaches to one when the data are fit by a better curve.

Figure 4 shows an algorithm used in the AutoShift program. The inputs are time-dependent test data points, such as creep compliance, storage modulus or CER¹ strength, at various temperatures. User must set a reference temperature and an approximate glass transition temperature.

The data points at each temperature are then fitted with the least-square method. After setting a reference curve at the reference temperature, the data points at an elevated temperature (T_i) are mapped and shifted onto the reference curve. The shifted data points along with the reference data points are fitted to form a new reference curve. If the new curve is not fitted well enough, the order of the polynomial (M) increases by one until it finds a best fit. Time-temperature shift factor is calculated by the amount of the horizontal distance in the time scale. This job repeats for the next temperatures.

Figure 4: Flow chart for AutoShift program.

EXAMPLES

The AutoShift program is applied to six different cases; Two cases on a non-destructive property (creep compliance) and four cases on a destructive property (CER strength):

- 1) Creep compliance of a PMMA material (named Plexus).
- 2) Creep compliance of an epoxy material (named Mavidon).
- 3) CER strength of pitch-based carbon fiber composite material (named XN40/25C).

¹ CER stands for Constant Elongation Rate.

- 4) CER strength of a tubular-lap bonded joint with Plexus adhesive.
- 5) CER strength of a tubular-lap bonded joint with Mavidon adhesive.
- 6) CER strength of a tubular-lap bolted joint.

Figure 5 shows test configurations and dimensions of the test specimens to obtain the time- and temperature-dependent test data. Table 1 lists the input parameters for the AutoShift program, and some outputs such as reliability and activation energies.

Figure 6 shows the test data and fitted curves on the measured time scales as well as the shifted time scales. The shifted data points are smoothly fitted with the master curves at all cases. This smoothness of the master curves indicates that the time-temperature superposition is applicable to the destructive strength properties as well as the non-destructive properties. Figure 7 shows the time-temperature shift factors and bi-linearly fitted lines.

Table 1: Input and output parameters for the AutoShift program.

Case Number	T _o [°C]	T _g [°C]	Order of Polynomial	R ² [%]	<i>DH</i> ₁ [KJ/mol]	<i>DH</i> ₂ [KJ/mol]
1	40	62	4	99.9	240.95	—
2	40	62	6	99.9	299.30	538.54
3	25	130	4	99.4	77.12	436.79
4	60	62	3	99.1	181.13	261.22
5	60	62	2	98.8	260.71	397.50
6	80	90	3	97.3	126.00	646.19

Figure 5: Test configurations and dimensions of test specimens (unit is in [mm]).

(Case 1)

(Case 2)

(Case 3)

(Case 4)

(Case 5)

(Case 6)

Figure 6: Time- and temperature dependent creep compliance or CER strength of various materials and jointed systems, and their master curves at reference temperatures.

Figure 7: Time-temperature shift factors and bi-linearly fitted lines.

CONCLUSIONS

The time-temperature superposition hypothesis can be used to estimate the life of the structures quickly through the time-temperature shifting. The shifting becomes fast, objective and user-independent with an automated shifting program, AutoShift. The automated shifting is successfully applied to several non-destructive and destructive properties of several materials and structures to obtain well-fitted master curves and shift factors.

The automated shifting is useful for not only the design of the structures, but acceleration of the accelerating tests. Since the shifting process is quick and automatic, the designer can estimate how the time and the temperature are superposed, and determine what the next step of tests should be. This decision during the full matrix of the test sequence may eliminate redundant or less-important set of tests, and thus reduce the number of test specimens and cost.

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